

Components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Programme: Is There Literacy Skills Deficiency among Grade Five Learners in Nyimba District?

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Abstract

The study investigated the components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program in Nyimba district and examined whether there were literacy skills deficiencies among grade five learners. Explanatory sequential research design was used on 142 study participants. Through interviews with grade teachers, six core components: phonemic awareness, phonics instruction, reading fluency, vocabulary, reading comprehension and writing were identified as essential for effective literacy education. Analysis of pre-test data revealed alarming deficiencies, particularly in vocabulary, dictation, story writing, pronunciation and sentence fluency, indicating inadequate foundational skills among students. Deficits in these areas hindered academic performance, access to complex texts and critical thinking opportunities. Contributing factors included a lack of English dictionaries, insufficient storybooks and teacher disorientation regarding effective literacy instruction methods. The findings underscore the necessity of a comprehensive literacy framework that integrates all components of literacy, providing adequate resources, and enhance teacher training. By addressing these challenges, the study advocates for improved literacy outcomes, ultimately fostering a stronger foundation for lifelong learning in resource-constrained educational environments.

Keywords: *phonemic awareness, vocabulary, comprehension, components, foundational literacy.*

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Introduction

The 2013 Zambia National Literacy Framework (ZNLf) was developed to replace the defunct Primary Reading Programme (PRP) which had New Breakthrough to Literacy (NBTL), Step into English (SITE) and Read on Course (ROC) (Nyimbili, 2021). The Literacy Framework was premised on Early Grade Reading with clear focus on teaching literacy skills to learners from grade 1 - 4 in familiar or local languages (MESVTEE, 2013; Mwanza, 2020). The assumptions of this policy framework were that learners by fourth grade would have become phonetically aware, relate letters to sounds (phonics), read with fluency, understand vocabulary, read comprehension passages in both local language and English and write short stories. Therefore, when English is introduced as a Medium of Instruction in all subjects by the fifth-grade learners should have transitioned to “speech and writing skills that could be used in other subjects” (MESVTEE, 2013:6). In principle, the crafters of the 2013 National Literacy Framework

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envisioned that by fifth grade all learners who passed through grade 1-4 should read and write with proficiency. However, recent studies have shown that literacy levels at grade five were still low despite a well-articulated literacy policy in place (Mandyata et al., 2023; Serpell, 2023; Mwanza, 2020; Zulu, 2019; Phiri, 2015). The question that begged for answers was: which components of the Primary School Literacy Instruction Program exhibited literacy skills deficiency among grade five learners in Nyimba district? To answer this question, the current study investigated the components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program in light of the increasing concerns about low reading proficiency levels among students. By addressing these issues, it was desired to facilitate the development of more effective and engaging literacy instruction programs that equips learners with literacy skills needed to succeed academically and beyond.

Literature Review

Emerging research has identified the vital role of high-quality literacy instruction in the classroom as a key determinant of students' academic success (Mandyata et al., 2023; Mofu et al., 2023). In fact, high-quality literacy instructions have been shown to be more influential than both the school and home environments (Mwanza-Kabaghe, 2022). While literacy programs can be customized to meet the diverse needs of different student groups, Elston et al (2022) argue that effective programs consistently integrate essential components such as phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, comprehension and writing into literacy education. When effectively integrated, these literacy skills have power to enable students navigate various texts and contexts with ease (MESVTEE, 2013). Thus, teachers should master the art of integration of literacy skills within their teaching practices to help learners advance beyond simply memorizing vowels and alphabet notations.

Phonemic awareness as a foundational skill in literacy development, enables learners to hear, identify and manipulate individual sounds in spoken words. Research by Ehri (2022) emphasised that mastering phonemic awareness facilitates understanding of the sound structure of language. Godoy, Pinheiro and Citoler (2017) found that teaching phonemic awareness was a significant predictor of reading and writing success among Brazilian children. Mofu et al. (2023) investigated the impact of book-reading activities at home on first graders' phonological awareness in Lusaka Province and highlighted the importance of blending and end-sound discrimination skills for literacy development. Johnston and Watson (2005) further demonstrated that systematic phonemic awareness instruction positively influences decoding and spelling abilities, reinforcing its critical role in literacy programs. Effective teaching strategies for phonemic awareness include activities such as sound discrimination, blending, segmenting and manipulation (Gabriel and Mpofu, 2024).

Phonics instruction is another foundational component of early literacy which emphasizes the systematic relationship between letters and sounds to support decoding and spelling skills (Ehri, 2020). Research highlights its effectiveness in improving reading outcomes, particularly when taught explicitly and systematically (Castles et al., 2018). A study in Australia, demonstrated that phonics instruction enhances literacy skills across diverse contexts (Scull and Lyons, 2024). Effective phonics teaching involves structured approaches that guide learners through letter-sound relationships, progressing from simple to complex patterns (Piasta and Hudson, 2022). This method ensures learners can decode unfamiliar words and build a strong foundation for reading fluency. Key strategies for teaching phonics include explicit instruction in phoneme-grapheme correspondences, blending sounds to form words and decoding practice using texts with specific phonic patterns (Woore, 2022).

Reading fluency, defined as the ability to read with speed, accuracy, and expression, is crucial for comprehension and overall literacy development (Bessette, 2020). Effective strategies for teaching fluency include repeated reading, choral reading, echo reading and sight word practice. Repeated reading involves learners revisiting the same text multiple times to enhance word recognition and automaticity (Van Bergen et al., 2021). Choral reading allows students to read aloud together in synchrony, improving rhythm and pacing. Echo reading engages learners in mimicking a proficient reader's phrasing and

intonation, fostering expressive reading (Bessette, 2020). Additionally, sight word practice reinforces recognition through interactive tools like flashcards or games (Gabriel and Mpofo, 2024). These methods collectively build confidence and fluency, enabling learners to read effortlessly and comprehend texts more effectively. Research highlights that fluency bridges word recognition with comprehension by freeing cognitive resources for meaning-making (Chard et al., 2008).

Vocabulary knowledge is another important literacy component that encompasses not only the spelling and pronunciation of words but also their meanings, syntactic features and appropriate usage in context (Nation, 1990). Research indicates a strong correlation between vocabulary knowledge and various language skills, including listening, speaking, reading and writing (Akbarian, 2018). Consequently, vocabulary instruction plays a critical role in literacy education, necessitating effective strategies to enhance learners' vocabulary acquisition. To address the challenge of vocabulary instruction, Hafsaari et al. (2025) identified several effective vocabulary teaching techniques, including memorization, using word cards and matching words with images. These strategies not only cater to different learning styles but also encourage active engagement with the language, as students are motivated to use English in practical contexts such as watching films and playing games. While these techniques have proven beneficial for adult learners, it remains crucial to explore their applicability to younger learners. Emerging technologies and social media platforms have also been identified as valuable resources for vocabulary instruction (Rajayi and Maleki, 2023). For instance, the use of podcasts has gained traction as an effective method for enhancing vocabulary knowledge (Putman and Kingsley, 2009). By integrating technology into the classroom, teachers can create a more interactive and engaging learning environment, which may lead to improved vocabulary retention and comprehension among students. Sewbihon-Getie (2020) suggested incorporating lexical approaches that focus on collocations and chunks to enhance vocabulary acquisition.

Reading comprehension is another crucial higher-order skill that significantly influences academic success. It is the ability to understand, interpret and analyse texts (Mkandawire, 2022). Reading comprehension involves efficient decoding and linguistic understanding, enabling students to derive meaning from texts (Elleman and Oslund, 2019). To teach reading comprehension, explicit teaching strategies (ETS) have been recommended as effective methods for enhancing literacy skills. A study by Mandyata et al. (2024) in Zambia, supports the notion that explicit instruction can bridge literacy gaps, particularly when transitioning from learning to read to reading to learn. Various comprehension strategies, such as reciprocal teaching, story mapping, think-alouds, questioning, visualizing, summarizing and predicting have been identified as effective tools to enhance learners' understanding and engagement with texts (Mežek et al., 2022; Ali and Razali, 2019). These strategies encourage active participation and critical thinking, essential components for developing strong comprehension skills. Furthermore, Hall et al. (2021) recognized narrative instruction as a powerful approach to improving reading comprehension, as it enhances narrative proficiency.

Writing is equally another important literacy component which scholars have identified (Dar and Khan, 2015; Ghabool et al., 2012). Teaching writing skills to children is a critical component of literacy education, particularly as writing plays a significant role in both academic and professional contexts (Muslem et al., 2022). The ability to express ideas coherently and creatively is essential, yet many students, especially those learning English as a second language (ESL) face enormous challenges in mastering this skill. Factors contributing to writing difficulties include inadequate grammar, punctuation and vocabulary skills as well as issues with anxiety and organizational structure (Fareed et al, 2016). Furthermore, Yunus and Chan (2016) believe the lack of effective pedagogical strategies, absence of trained teachers and insufficient practice opportunities, exacerbates the writing challenges faced by learners. Selvaraj and Aziz (2019) identified effective teaching strategies to enhance writing skills among children such as scaffolding techniques, collaborative learning and the provision of feedback from both teachers and peers. Additionally, the use of rubrics and direct feedback has been recommended for higher education contexts to guide student assessments (Mahmoudi, 2020). Blended learning, which combines traditional in-person instruction with online learning, has also emerged as an innovative approach to teaching writing, offering

flexibility and accessibility to students (Adas and Bakir, 2013). Overall, employing diverse and effective methodologies in teaching writing can better equip learners for their future educational success.

Despite extensive global evidence highlighting the significance of integrating foundational literacy skills such as phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, comprehension and writing into classroom practice, little is known about the actual state of these skills among learners in rural Zambian contexts. While broad policy frameworks and pedagogical models advocate for comprehensive literacy instruction, there remains limited empirical investigation into whether learners at the middle primary school level in Nyimba District have adequately acquired these skills. The absence of localised research creates uncertainty about whether literacy instruction translates into measurable competences, particularly in environments where resources, teacher capacity and home literacy support may vary considerably. This knowledge gap necessitated an inquiry into the extent of literacy skills deficiency among Grade Five learners in Nyimba District to inform both policy and instructional practice tailored to the realities of such contexts.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study utilised explanatory sequential research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to gain a comprehensive understanding of the literacy instruction program and the literacy skills deficiencies among grade five learners in Nyimba District, Zambia. In this type of research design, researchers conduct quantitative research first followed by qualitative research to provide further explanation for the quantitative research results (Muchanga, 2024). The quantitative component involved pre-tests to assess literacy skills, while the qualitative component consisted of interviews and classroom observations to gather insights from teachers regarding the literacy instruction program and factors contributing to observed deficiencies.

Participants

The participants in this study included 140 grade five learners of age between 10-15 years from two urban primary schools in Nyimba District, as well as 2 grade five teachers who were responsible for teaching literacy in English. The selection of learners and schools was based on purposive and simple random sampling.

Data Collection

a. Quantitative Data Collection

To assess literacy skills, researcher-made pre-test was administered to all 140 grade five learners. The pre-test evaluated various literacy components, including: pronunciation, audio listening, grammar, vocabulary, sentence fluency, comprehension, dictation, punctuation, speed reading and phonemic awareness. The pre-test was designed to provide a baseline measurement of students' literacy skills, allowing for the identification of specific deficiencies. The data collected from the pre-test were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores and standard deviations. Prior to data collection a pilot study was conducted with 62 students aimed at validating the instruments and checking internal consistency of the questions. The result of the pilot test was subjected to expert analysis in measurement and evaluation to establish the validity and reliability index of the instruments. Thus, they fulfilled the reliability requirements, obtaining a Cronbach Alpha of $\alpha = 0.97$.

b. Qualitative Data Collection

Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews with grade five teachers and direct classroom observations for 12 weeks. The interviews aimed to explore teachers' perspectives on the components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program and the challenges faced in implementing effective literacy instruction. Questions were designed to elicit detailed responses regarding literacy components, teaching strategies, and resource availability. Classroom observations were

conducted to gain insights into the teaching practices and classroom environment related to literacy instruction. Observations focused on the integration of literacy components, student engagement and the availability of teaching resources.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data from the pre-test were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the performance of students across the various literacy components. Mean scores and standard deviations were calculated to highlight areas of strength and weakness in literacy skills. Qualitative data from interviews and classroom observations were transcribed and analyzed thematically. Key themes and patterns were identified to understand the factors contributing to literacy skill deficiencies and the effectiveness of the literacy instruction program. This qualitative analysis complemented the quantitative findings, providing a holistic view of the literacy challenges faced by students.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Zambia, Humanities and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee (HSSREC) IORG No.0005376 / IRB No. 00006464/ REF No. 2024: APR-055 to carry out the study in Nyimba District and from relevant educational authorities at provincial, district and school level prior to data collection. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, including teachers and parents of the learners. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, ensuring that participants' identities were protected in reporting the findings.

Results

Components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program

To answer the question of what components constituted the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program in Nyimba district, an interview schedule was conducted with two grade five teachers. One teacher said:

“.....in addition I don't pay attention to phonemic awareness and phonics because these are skills that must be taught at lower primary. In grade five we teach listening and speaking spellings, reading, writing and language structure. I include dictation, read alouds, word games, grammar and sentence construction”. Another teacher said: “I follow the grade five English book which mainly has reading comprehension on various issues, grammar, vocabulary and writing”.

The teachers affirmed the components as summarized in table 1 below:

Table 1. Components of the Zambian Primary School Literacy Instruction Program

Phonemic awareness
Phonics instruction
Reading Fluency
Vocabulary
Reading Comprehension
Writing

The data provided in table 1 show components of Primary School Literacy Instruction Programme offered in Nyimba district. It includes: phonemic awareness, phonics instruction, reading fluency, vocabulary, reading comprehension and writing skills.

Literacy Skills Deficiencies among Grade Five Learners in Nyimba District

To answer whether there were significant literacy skills deficiencies among grade five learners in Nyimba district, pre-tests were used as baseline. The pre-tests variables were: pronunciation, audio listening, grammar, vocabulary, sentence fluency, comprehension, dictation, punctuation, speed reading and

phonemic awareness. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics as shown in table 2 below including mean scores and standard deviations to highlight strength and weakness in literacy skills.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Pretest Scores of Literacy Skills Deficiencies

Literacy component	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pronunciation	140	41.39	25.751
Audio Listening	140	53.64	36.348
Grammar	140	50.39	23.345
Vocabulary	140	22.07	23.429
Sentence Fluency	140	32.24	22.936
Comprehension	140	56.43	28.564
Dictation	140	25.84	28.782
Story Writing	140	23.68	24.178
Punctuation	140	61.25	24.875
Speed Reading	140	47.52	23.829
Phonemic Awareness	140	46.94	22.426
Valid N (listwise)	140		

Factors that Contributed to Observed Deficiencies in Literacy Skills

In order to explain why there were disparities and significant literacy deficiencies in the identified literacy components, classroom observations and interviews with grade teachers were conducted during a calendar school term. The factors that contributed to observed deficiencies in literacy skills were summarised in table 3 below:

Table 3. Factors that Contributed to Observed Deficiencies in Literacy Skills

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of English dictionaries to teach vocabulary • Inadequate storybooks for individual and group reading • Teacher disorientation on how to integrate literacy components in pedagogy • Most students transitioned to grade five with insufficient knowledge of letter sounds, letter formation, phrase, grammar, vocabulary and spelling

Discussion of Findings

The study found that despite Zambia’s primary school literacy policy including internationally recognised essential components like phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension and writing (MESVTEE, 2013; MoE, 1996, 2023, 2025; Serenje, 2024; Gabriel and Mpofu, 2024; Serpell, 2023; Mandyata et al., 2023; Scull and Lyons, 2024; Firat and Koyuncu, 2020; UNESCO, 2020; Ehri, 2022), sampled Grade Five learners in Nyimba District demonstrated considerable deficiencies in vocabulary, dictation, story writing, pronunciation and sentence fluency. These skills were critical for effective communication and academic success. For instance, vocabulary underpins comprehension and expression, enabling learners to decode and articulate ideas (Grabe and Stoller, 2018). Dictation supports spelling, listening and writing accuracy, vital for orthographic competence (Muslem et al., 2022; Kaani, 2021). Story writing develops narrative ability, creativity and coherent thought organization (Selvaraj and Aziz, 2019). Pronunciation influences oral communication clarity and learner confidence (Nation, 1990), while sentence fluency ensures writing coherence and readability (Bessette, 2020). Deficits in these areas hindered academic performance and limited long-term literacy development which restricted access to

complex texts and critical thinking opportunities. These results align with Mwanza (2020) and Kombe and Mwanza (2019) who documented similar instructional gaps in some districts in Zambia. However, the current study revealed broader skill deficits than writing challenges reported by Phiri (2015) in Lusaka, suggesting that rural districts face more severe literacy issues due to systemic barriers.

Given the foundational role of these literacy skills, addressing this literacy gap demand urgent and multifaceted action, probably, a push toward strategic resource allocation, enhanced teacher professional development and the integration of innovative pedagogies. Thus, prioritising investments in rural and remote schools maybe a plus in ensuring access to quality learning materials, technology and well-trained teachers. By translating research findings into actionable policy changes, Zambia can effectively bridge literacy gaps between policy and implementation thereby empower learners and foster equitable educational opportunities for all.

The discrepancy between curriculum intent and classroom practice revealed in this study points to a critical implementation gap that remains insufficiently addressed in existing literature. While previous research has documented isolated challenges such as inadequate teacher preparation (Kombe, 2017), resource scarcity (Mwanza, 2020) or weak monitoring systems (MoE, 2019), the present findings are novel in showing how these factors interact synergistically to undermine curriculum fidelity in literacy education. Teachers lack of pedagogical knowledge and skills required to deliver comprehensive literacy instruction is concerning. This gap is particularly detrimental because effective literacy teaching demand a nuanced understanding of both foundational skills such as phonological awareness, decoding and vocabulary development; and higher-order processes, including comprehension, synthesis and written expression. Without this expertise, instruction often defaults to rote learning and fragmented activities that fail to equip learners with transferable, functional literacy skills. This aligns with Kamalata's (2016) findings in North Western Province, where teachers were found to have insufficient training in phonological awareness and language transition strategies. Similarly, Kombe and Mwanza (2019) reported that teachers in Kitwe were inadequately prepared by education authorities to teach literacy effectively. This implies that the prevalence of rote learning approaches and an overemphasis on less demanding literacy components observed in this study underscore the urgent need for evidence-based, innovative pedagogical practices. Within this context, storytelling as demonstrated in the current research emerges as a promising supplementary approach that is capable of fostering both foundational literacy skills and higher-order competencies.

Secondly, the lack of basic instructional materials such as English dictionaries, storybooks and phonics resources was a consistent theme among teacher responses. This finding corroborates Mwanza's (2020) observation regarding the persistent inadequacy of contextually relevant learning materials in rural Zambian schools. Similarly, Mandyata et al. (2024), in their study of four primary schools in Serenje district, reported that a recurrent challenge was the scarcity of appropriate teaching and learning resources necessary to facilitate a smooth transition to Grade Five. Instructional materials are indispensable in literacy instruction because they provide structured opportunities for learners to engage with language in varied, authentic and meaningful contexts. They enable repeated exposure to vocabulary, support comprehension through diverse texts and scaffold the gradual mastery of reading and writing skills. The absence of such materials deprives learners of repeated and meaningful exposure to language which is an essential condition for vocabulary development, syntactic mastery and writing fluency. As a result, the provision of adequate and contextually suitable resources to learners in primary schools should be regarded as a critical priority in any literacy reform initiative. Thus, special attention should be given to learners in rural areas where resource deficits are most acute.

To address these multifaceted challenges, the study recommends a restructured teacher training model that emphasises integrated and culturally relevant pedagogies, including storytelling. Therefore, policymakers must also ensure that literacy instruction is supported by continuous professional development, resource provision and monitoring mechanisms. There must be a deliberate promotion of equitable access to teaching and learning materials such as storybooks and dictionaries especially in rural schools. Additionally, national literacy policies should be reviewed to include clear guidelines on

implementing blended approaches. Perhaps, literacy instruction in Zambia requires a paradigm shift towards blended, context-sensitive and evidence-based approaches. The study highlights the pressing need for reforms in curriculum delivery, teacher capacity and resource allocation. Further research could investigate how digital tools might support multimodal literacy development in under-resourced contexts. With coordinated efforts among stakeholders, Zambia can move closer to achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number 4 of the United Nations (UN) calling for quality, equitable and sustainable literacy outcomes for all learners by 2030.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is evident that Zambia's literacy policy must move beyond rhetorical alignment with international frameworks toward deliberate, context-sensitive implementation that bridges the gap between policy and classroom realities. A clear policy direction should prioritise sustained investment in teacher professional development with emphasis on integrated and culturally relevant pedagogies such as storytelling, alongside systematic provision of contextually appropriate instructional resources for rural and underserved schools. Equally, literacy reforms must embed robust monitoring mechanisms to ensure curriculum fidelity, while revising national frameworks to explicitly incorporate blended approaches that integrate foundational skills, higher-order competencies and multimodal practices. Such a comprehensive and equity-driven strategy would not only strengthen learner outcomes in critical areas like vocabulary, writing fluency and comprehension but also advance Zambia's commitment to inclusive and sustainable education in line with SDG 4.

Limitations

The study's focus on grade five learners may not fully capture the literacy challenges faced by students in other grades. Future research could expand the sample to include a broader range of participants and explore longitudinal changes in literacy skills over time.

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